

Integration of Arabica coffee into the AquaCrop model: First approach

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Information 1 – Description and adjustments of AquaCrop: conservative and crop-specific parameters

The conservative and crop-specific parameters of Arabica coffee were obtained from an extensive literature review (Table 1) covering the wide range of Arabica coffee cultivars most commonly cultivated in Brazil, such as Mundo Novo, Catuaí, Obatã, and Acaiaí (Pezzopane *et al.*, 2003; Oliveira *et al.*, 2021). Parameter adjustments were refined through an iterative trial-and-error approach during the calibration process.

Conservative parameters related to water stress coefficients (Ks) followed a similar iterative approach during the AquaCrop Fortran Model (AQF) calibration process (Table 1). Ks acts as a modifier of AQF conservative parameters, ranging from Ks = 1 (no stress) to Ks = zero (maximum stress) (Raes *et al.*, 2018). The calibrated values of these coefficients used in this study are detailed in Table 1.

Table 1- Conservative and crop-specific parameters (and their respective values) required for the simulation of Arabica coffee yield by the AquaCrop Fortran model.

Simbol	Description	Type ^{(1),(2),(3)}	Values	Reference
1. Crop phenology				
1.1 Threshold air temperatures				
Tb	Base temperature (°C)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	10.5 °C	Pezzopane et al. (2008)
TB	Upper temperature (°C)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	32.0 °C	Iaffe et al. (2001); Lima and Silva (2008)
1.2 Development of green canopy cover				
	Number of plants per hectare	Conservative ⁽²⁾	6,000	Mesquita et al. (2016); Silva et al. (2021)
	Accumulated growing degree days (GDD; °C day ⁻¹): Time from transplanting ⁽⁴⁾ to recovered transplanting.	Conservative ⁽¹⁾		Excluded for Arabica coffee due to the analysis

CGC	Canopy growth coefficient (% GDD ⁻¹)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾	0.054571	focusing on mature crops.
CDC	Canopy decline coefficient (% GDD ⁻¹)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.002520	Calibrated by the present study.
CCx	Maximum canopy cover as shaded area fractions (%)	Conservative ⁽²⁾	60 %	Almeida et al. (2017)
	GDD: Time from transplanting ⁽⁴⁾ to start senescence	Crop-specific ⁽³⁾	2,390 °C day ⁻¹	Calculated in this study from experimental data from Pezzopane et al. (2003) ⁽⁵⁾
	GDD: Time from transplanting ⁽⁴⁾ to maturity, i.e., length of crop cycle	Crop-specific ⁽³⁾	3,446 °C day ⁻¹	
1.3 Flowering				
	Time from transplanting ⁽⁴⁾ to flowering	Crop-specific ⁽³⁾	494 °C day ⁻¹	Calculated in this study from experimental data from Pezzopane et al. (2003) ⁽⁵⁾
	Length of the flowering stage	Crop-specific ⁽³⁾	107 °C day ⁻¹	Default
	Crop determinacy linked with flowering	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	Sim	AquaCrop.
1.4 Development of root zone				
	Minimum effective rooting depth (m)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	1.0 m	For the adult plant. Franco and Inforzato (1946); Silva et al. (2009), Rosa et al. (2010)
	Maximum effective rooting depth (m)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	1.0 m	
SxTopQ	Maximum root water extraction at top of the root zone (m ³ m ⁻³ day ⁻¹)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.048	
SxBotQ	Maximum root water extraction at the bottom of the root zone (m ³ m ⁻³ day ⁻¹)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.012	Calibrated by the present study.
2. Crop transpiration				
KcTr,x	Crop coefficient when canopy is complete but prior to senescence	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.60 dimensionless	Gutiérrez and Meinzer (1994), Oliveira et al. (2003)
	Decline of crop coefficient (% day ⁻¹) as a result of ageing, nitrogen deficiency, etc.	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.319	Calibrated by the present study.
	Effect of canopy cover on reducing soil evaporation in late season stage	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	95%	Default AquaCrop.
3. Biomass production and yield formation				
3.1 Crop water productivity				
WP*	Water productivity normalized for ETo and CO ₂ (gram m ⁻²)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	15 gram m ⁻²	Raes et al. (2018b)
	Water productivity normalized for ETo and CO ₂ during yield formation (as percent WP* before yield formation)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	100	Default AquaCrop.
3.2 Harvest Index				
Hlo	Reference harvest index (%)	Conservative ⁽²⁾	10%	Almeida et al. (2017)
	Possible increase (%) of HI due to water stress before flowering	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	13%	
	Excess of potential fruits (%)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	50%	
	Coefficient describing positive impact of restricted vegetative growth during yield formation on HI	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.7	Calibrated by the present study.
	Coefficient describing negative impact of stomatal closure during yield formation on HI	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0	
	Allowable maximum increase (%) of specified HI	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	23%	Awati et al. (2013); Almeida et al. (2017)

4. Stresses

4.1 Soil water stresses

	Soil water depletion threshold for canopy expansion - Upper threshold	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.31	
K _{S_{exp,w}}	Soil water depletion threshold for canopy expansion - Lower threshold	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.66	
	Shape factor for water stress coefficient for canopy expansion	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	2.5	
	Soil water depletion threshold for stomatal control - Upper threshold	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.30	
K _{S_{sto}}	Shape factor for Water stress coefficient for stomatal control	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	1.4	Calibrated by the present study.
	Soil water depletion threshold for canopy senescence - Upper threshold	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.41	
K _{S_{sen}}	Shape factor for Water stress coefficient for canopy senescence	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	1.3	
	Soil water depletion threshold for failure of pollination - Upper threshold	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	0.75	
K _{S_{pol,w}}				
K _{S_{aer}}	Soil water stress coefficient for waterlogging (aeration stress) (K _{S_{aer}})	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	5%	
	4.2 Air temperature stress			
	Minimum air temperature below which pollination starts to fail (cold stress) (°C)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	10.0 °C	
	Maximum air temperature above which pollination starts to fail (heat stress) (°C)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	34.0 °C	Calibrated by the present study.
	Minimum growing degrees required for full biomass production (°C day ⁻¹)	Conservative ⁽¹⁾	10.8 °C	

⁽¹⁾ Conservative generally applicable; ⁽²⁾ Conservative related to management; ⁽³⁾ Crop-specific; ⁽⁴⁾ The transplanting date was replaced with the dormancy start date (vegetative rest) = August 1, considered the appropriate simulation start date for perennial species like Arabica coffee; ⁽⁵⁾ The calculation method and accumulated growing degree days (GDD; °C day⁻¹) values for each reproductive development stage are provided in Information 2 and Table 2.

Information 2 - Obtaining data on the accumulation of growing degree days

Accumulated Growing Degree Day (GDD) data are scarce in the literature for Arabica coffee prior to flowering. Since these data are crucial for AquaCrop, GDD was calculated for each growth stage, from dormancy to fruit ripening.

As the AQF (version 6.1) does not include a perennial crop option, the transplant date was replaced with the dormancy stage start date, set as August 1st, following Pezzopane *et al.* (2003). Therefore, to calculate the accumulated GDD, the scale (and phenological stages) proposed by Pezzopane *et al.* (2003) was adopted. This approach involved: i) start dates for dormancy (August 1st) and the completion of each reproductive growth stage, as provided by Pezzopane *et al.* (2003) and, ii) daily maximum (Tasmax) and minimum (Tasmin) air

temperature data from the BR-DWGD dataset (Xavier *et al.*, 2022).

The daily mean air temperature (Tas) was obtained from the arithmetic mean of Tasmx and Tasmin. The accumulated GDD was obtained by (Raes *et al.*, 2018):

$$GDD = \sum_{i=1}^n Tas - Tb \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

when $Tas \leq Tb$, then $STd = 0$.

where: GDD = accumulated growing degree days from August 1st to the last day of each reproductive growth stage during the 2001/2002 agricultural year ($^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$; Table 2), Tas = daily mean air temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), Tb = base temperature for Arabica coffee (10.5°C) (Pezzopane *et al.*, 2008), i = August 1st (Pezzopane *et al.*, 2003), n = completion date of each reproductive growth stage (Pezzopane *et al.*, 2003).

Table 2- Accumulated growing degree days (GDD; $^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$) for the entire reproductive phase of Arabica coffee development, considering the stages: dormancy (0), swollen bud (1), floral bud development (2), flowering (3), post-flowering (4), pinhead (5), fruit expansion (6), fruit hardening (7), fruit grain filling (8), and fruit ripening (9). A base temperature (TB) of 10.5°C was used for the GDD calculation (Pezzopane *et al.*, 2008).

Cultivar	Municipalities	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	3 to 5
Mundo Novo IAC 388-17	Campinas (SP)	199	207	314	354	375	429	884	1637	2795	2949	89
Catuai Vermelho IAC 144	Campinas (SP)	199	207	314	354	375	429	994	1706	2893	3051	89
IAC Obatã	Campinas (SP)	199	207	314	354	375	429	994	1829	3266	3438	89
Acaia IAC 474-16	Mococa (SP)	31	244	585	634	698	747	1454	2123	3425	3645	126
Catuai Amarelo IAC 62	Mococa (SP)	31	244	585	634	698	747	1454	2123	3425	3745	126
IAC Obatã	Mococa (SP)	31	244	585	634	698	747	1567	2319	3745	3849	126
Mean GDD ($^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$):		115	226	450	494	536	588	1225	1956	3258	3446	107

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